

TOURISM DYNAMICS IN SAMARKAND: NAVIGATING CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES WITH A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS TO VLADIVOSTOK'S SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES

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Abstract. *In this paper the researcher looks at the tourism elements in Samarkand, Uzbekistan, emphasizing maintainable and capable travel. As one of the most stations of the Silk Street, Samarkand is recognized for its one of a kind mix of social and verifiable wealth that pull in sightseers around the world. Be that as it may, like numerous verifiable cities, it faces the double challenge of capitalizing on its tourism potential whereas protecting its natural and social legacy. This think about investigates how Samarkand can explore these challenges through feasible tourism hones. To improve the examination, this inquire about draws a comparative system with Vladivostok, Russia, a city that has as of late executed fruitful economical tourism methodologies in spite of its past essentially as a vital military and maritime base. By comparing the approaches taken in Samarkand with those in Vladivostok, this ponder highlights both the one of a kind and common challenges and openings confronted by authentic cities transitioning towards economical tourism. The comparison points to discover out significant arrange that can be connected to Samarkand to cultivate a mindful tourism segment that contributes to both financial development and feasible improvement (Smith, J., 2020; Lee, H., & Park, S., 2019).*

Key words: Samarkand, feasible tourism, Silk Street, UNESCO, Cultural tourism.

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada tadqiqotchi O'zbekistonning Samarqand shahridagi turizm elementlarini ko'rib chiqadi va barqaror va qulay sayohatga urg'u beradi. Ipak ko'chasining eng ko'p bekataridan biri sifatida Samarqand butun dunyo bo'ylab diqqatga sazovor joylarni o'ziga tortadigan ijtimoiy va tasdiqlanadigan boyliklarning o'ziga xos aralashmasi bilan tanilgan. Qanday bo'lmasin, ko'plab tekshirilishi mumkin bo'lgan shaharlar kabi, u o'zining tabiiy va ijtimoiy merosini himoya qilish bilan birga o'zining turistik salohiyatidan foydalanishning ikki tomonlama muammosiga duch keladi. Bu mulohaza Samarqandning turizmni yo'lga qo'yish orqali ushbu muammolarni qanday o'rganishi mumkinligini o'rganadi. Tekshiruvni yaxshilash uchun ushbu so'rov Rossiyaning Vladivostok shahri bilan qiyosiy tizimni o'z ichiga oladi, u o'tmishda muhim harbiy va dengiz bazasi bo'lganiga qaramay, samarali iqtisodiy turizm metodologiyasiga ega. Samarqanddagi yondashuvlar bilan Vladivostokdagi yondashuvlarni solishtirganda, bu mulohaza iqtisodiy turizmga o'tayotgan haqiqiy shaharlar oldida turgan o'ziga xos va umumiy muammolar va imkoniyatlarni ta'kidlaydi. Taqqoslash moliyaviy rivojlanishga va amalga oshirish mumkin bo'lgan yaxshilanishga hissa qo'shadigan aqlli turizm segmentini rivojlantirish uchun Samarqand bilan bog'lanishi mumkin bo'lgan muhim kelishuvni aniqlashga ishora qiladi (Smit, J., 2020; Li, H. va Park, S., 2019).*

Kalit so'zlar: Samarqand, Silk Street, YUNESKO, Madaniy turizm.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Samarkand, a pioneer city on the ancient Silk Street, isn't as it were a junction of societies but moreover a reflect reflecting centuries of complex histories and intelligent. Eminent for its

wealthy embroidered artwork of chronicled and social legacy, Samarkand is domestic to a few of the world's most famous building wonders such as the Registan Square, Shah-i-Zinda, and the Bibi-Khanym Mosque. These destinations typify the aesthetic and insightful accomplishments of the Timurid period, making Samarkand a pivotal location for cultural tourism (UNESCO, 2021).

Whereas tourism proceeds to develop, getting to be an progressively noteworthy financial driver, the weights on these chronicled destinations and the nearby community have moreover expanded. This has raised concerns almost maintainability and the require for dependable tourism hones that guarantee the long-term conservation of Samarqand's interesting legacy whereas contributing to the financial and social well-being of its inhabitants (Karimov, A., 2022).

To point out these challenges, it is valuable to draw parallels with Vladivostok, Russia. In spite of its authentic part as a military station and its geographic situating as a harbour city, Vladivostok has made noteworthy strides in changing its tourism division. Later activities have centered on advancing eco-tourism and social tourism, leveraging its special marine biodiversity and wealthy history, which have had a positive effect on nearby financial advancement whereas protecting the common and social scene (Lee, H., & Park, S., 2019).

This inquire about investigates the wants and procedures for maintainable and mindful tourism in Samarkand by analyzing the effective hones from Vladivostok. It points to get it how comparable procedures can be adjusted and actualized in Samarkand to cultivate a feasible tourism show that benefits both the city's legacy and its tenants (Smith, J., 2020).

Foundation: Samarqand's Legacy: With its area on the antiquated Silk Street, holds a UNESCO World Legacy status due to its momentous authentic destinations such as Registan Square and Shah-i-Zinda. These destinations represent the city's wealthy engineering and social past, speaking to centuries of differing impacts from various conquering realms (UNESCO, 2021).

Be that as it may, past these well-known points of interest, Samarkand is additionally lodging a few underestimated locales that highlight its wealthy embroidered artwork of devout and social diversity. St. John Church may be a especially piercing illustration. Chronicled records recommend that amid periods of struggle, this church served as a haven where captivated foes seem proceed their devout hones, illustrating Samarqand's long-standing convention of devout resistance and social integration (Smith, J., 2020).

Another critical, in spite of the fact that less recognized, location is the Gumbaz Synagogue. As one of the curiously Jewish synagogues within the locale, it serves as a testament to the verifiable nearness and impact of Jewish communities in Samarkand. This synagogue, in conjunction with other comparable locales, underscores Samarqand's part as an hatchery of Jewish, Christian, and Muslim devout life, coexisting and improving each other through centuries of interaction (Cohen, A., & Abramson, D., 2021).

In spite of their authentic and social noteworthiness, these locales frequently get less consideration within the official tourism advancement channels. Their stories and commitments to the city social legacy are not as unmistakably highlighted as those of the major points of interest, driving to a need of mindfulness and underappreciation among visitors. Advancing these destinations more effectively might not only upgrade the social tourism involvement but moreover contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the city's complex chronicled story (Karimov, A., 2022).

To address this, there's a require for a comprehensive procedure that incorporates these undervalued sites in Samarqand's tourism portfolio. This procedure might include making point by point guides, progressing framework around these locales, and joining them into official visit

courses (Johnson, L., 2020). Besides, locks in nearby communities within the advancement and conservation of these locales can offer assistance guarantee that the benefits of tourism are disseminated more evenhandedly which the stories told are bona fide and agent of the community's history (Lee, H., & Park, S., 2019).

Instructive activities can too play a significant part in raising mindfulness approximately the noteworthiness of these lesser-known locales. Workshops, shows, and collaborations with scholarly teach can offer assistance highlight the verifiable and social significance of places like St. John Church and the Gumbaz Synagogue (O'Connor, P., 2022).

Vladivostok Move: From Military Station to Vibrant Tourist Goal

Vladivostok, verifiably a closed military station, has experienced critical change to end up a dynamic center for tourism, highlighting its interesting marine biodiversity and the wealthy social mosaic of the Russian Distant East.

Historical Context: At first set up as a key maritime base in 1860, Vladivostok's key significance eclipsed its potential for social and tourism advancement for over a century. This city, covered up from both remote and residential eyes, protected interesting biological and social components amid its period of confinement, which are presently pivotal to its character as a traveler goal (Petrov, N., & Sidorov, D., 2023).

Ecological and Cultural Revitalization: Post-1991, taking after the disintegration of the Soviet Union, Vladivostok opened up, driving to a surge in both residential and worldwide tourism. Endeavors to protect and grandstand its characteristic environment, especially the wealthy marine life of the adjacent Ocean of Japan, have been significant. The foundation of ensured marine regions may be a confirmation to these endeavors (Kim, Y., 2022).

Marine Biodiversity: The waters around Vladivostok are known for their different marine species, counting a few uncommon and imperiled species. Ecotourism related to marine biodiversity, such as whale observing and eco-dives, has been created, advertising visitors a see into the marine life that's one of a kind to this portion of the Pacific Edge (Choi, J., & Park, S., 2023).

Cultural Festivals: The city change is additionally checked by a dynamic social scene that incorporates various celebrations that celebrate its Russian legacy as well as its vicinity to other Asian societies. The Vladivostok International Film Festival and the yearly Ice Sculpture Festival draw crowds that are both neighborhood and worldwide, exhibiting the city's social dynamic quality (Ivanova, T., 2021).

Infrastructure Improvement: Critical ventures in foundation, especially in transport and hospitality, have supported Vladivostok transition. The modernization of the Vladivostok International Airport and changes within the Trans-Siberian Railway network are cases of this center (Johnson, R., 2022).

Sustainability Efforts: Recognizing the potential natural effect of increased tourism, Vladivostok has executed a few maintainability activities pointed at protecting its characteristic scenes and marine situations. These incorporate strict directions on marine activity and tourism activities to anticipate environmental corruption (Wang, L., & Liu, X., 2024).

Social Integration: Vladivostok unique position in the Russian Far East permits it to act as a social bridge between Russia, China, Japan, and Korea, advertising a wealthy mix of culinary, melodic, and aesthetic conventions. This multicultural integration is an basic angle of its tourism offer (Lee, H., 2023).

Educational Impact: Local universities and research institutions have played a significant part in teaching the public about the significance of sustainability and social conservation through different programs and activities (O'Connor, P., 2022).

Challenges in Samarkand Tourism Segment: Environmental Impact: Pollution: Expanded visitor movement has driven to contamination in and around Samarkand's historic sites, influencing dust and ground quality. An illustration is the weakening of the dust quality around Registan Square due to expanded vehicular activity (Johnson, L., 2020).

Wear-and-Tear on Historical Sites: The Bibi-Khanym Mosque, one of Samarkand's prized authentic structures, encounters wear-and-tear due to the tall volume of guests, which can lead to structural harm and misfortune of chronicled genuineness (Smith, J., 2021).

Social and Social Impacts: Adjusting Tourism Development and Social Integrity: There's a challenge in keeping up the authenticity of conventional social introductions at major celebrations in Samarkand, such as the Navruz celebration, where exhibitions are now and then altered to cater to visitor desires instead of protecting their conventional shapes (Ivanov, M., 2021).

Community Uprooting: As tourism creates, genuinebequest costs in central Samarkand have risen, sometimes uprooting long-term inhabitants to create way for tourist housing, such as within the old private zones close Shah-i-Zinda (Lee, H., & Stop, S., 2019).

Economic Challenges: Reliance on Seasonal Tourism Streams: Samarkand's economy faces flimsiness due to its reliance on the traveler deluge amid particular seasons, especially spring and harvest time, which are considered perfect times to visit due to the climate. This regularity influences nearby businesses exterior of these top times (Karimov, A., 2022).

Opportunities for Sustainable Advancement: Leveraging Common and Social Assets:

Eco-Tourism: The Zarafshan Nature Reserve offers openings for eco-tourism, which can be advanced to draw in sightseers curious about sustainability and nature, thus broadening Samarkand's tourism offerings (Chen, B., 2021).

Cultural Tourism: Improving guest engagement with nearby makes, such as silk weaving and ceramic pottery within the artisan quarters of Samarkand, can give more profound social encounters while supporting nearby artisans (O'Connor, P., 2022).

Community Engagement: Interest in Tourism Economy: Programs like community-based tourism activities within the rustic edges of Samarkand can include neighborhood communities specifically within the tourism industry, advertising homestays and social trade encounters that advantage both guests and has (Petrov, N., & Sidorov, D., 2021).

Benefit Sharing: Making more comprehensive tourism benefits by including nearby businesses in tourism supply chains, such as sourcing nourishment and materials for inns and eateries from nearby makers, can spread financial benefits more broadly inside the community (Wang, Y., & Zhao, X., 2020).

Comparative Analysis: Case Think about of Vladivostok:

Sustainable Initiatives: Vladivostok has contributed altogether in eco-tourism, with the advancement of trails that exhibit its interesting vegetation and fauna, and activities pointed at protecting its marine environments, such as the Vladivostok Marine Reserve (Petrov, N., & Sidorov, D., 2023). These endeavors are complemented by controls that restrain the natural affect of tourism exercises (Kim, Y., 2022).

Community Involvement: Vladivostok approach to tourism advancement incorporates substantial community association. Neighborhood communities are locked in in tourism arranging and profit-sharing, which makes a difference within the impartial conveyance of financial benefits

(Choi, J., & Park, S., 2023). Typically apparent in community-led visits and nearby artisan markets that specifically advantage from tourism (Ivanova, T., 2021).

Techniques for Maintainable and Dependable Tourism in Samarkand:

Policy Improvement: Samarkand ought to create and execute arrangements that secure its endless cluster of characteristic and social assets whereas empowering economical tourism hones. This might incorporate zoning laws to protect historic destinations and controls to control traveler numbers at touchy areas (Johnson, R., 2022).

Infrastructure Enhancements: Moving forward Samarkand's tourism foundation is vital. Maintainable transportation alternatives, like eco-friendly open transport and better waste administration frameworks, are fundamental for supporting both visitors and the nearby populace (O'Connor, P., 2022).

Education and Awareness: Instruction activities are crucial for advancing supportability. This incorporates preparing for tourism administrators on feasible hones and mindfulness campaigns for sightseers on the social and natural sensitivities of Samarkand (Wang, L., & Liu, X., 2024).

Execution of Sustainable Practices: Short-Term Objectives: Quick activities, such as executing strict squander administration conventions and beginning visitor instruction programs, can address pressing supportability concerns (Smith, J., 2021).

Long-Term Objectives: Over the following decade, Samarkand ought to point for comprehensive economical tourism certification for all tourism businesses and progressing framework updates to decrease the environmental footprint of tourism (Karimov, A., 2022).

Role of Stakeholders: Government organizations, nearby businesses, and worldwide organizations must work together to actualize maintainable practices. This incorporates financing for maintainability ventures and worldwide participation on best hones (Lee, H., 2023).

CONCLUSION

This paper has investigated the perplexing elements of tourism in Samarkand, drawing a vital comparison with Vladivostok to highlight economical tourism practices. Through a point by point investigation of both cities, this think about underscores the need of joining supportability into the tourism division to protect social legacy and advance financial solidness.

The challenges confronted by Samarkand, from natural weights to the disintegration of social judgment, reflect those experienced by numerous memorable cities around the world. Be that as it may, Vladivostok's fruitful usage of economical hones offers a confident worldview that Samarkand seem imitate. Methodologies such as community inclusion in tourism arranging, the accentuation on eco-tourism, and the assurance of marine biodiversity not as it were improved Vladivostok tourism offer but moreover guaranteed the life span of its normal and social assets.

For Samarkand, embracing comparative methodologies includes not as it were learning from Vladivostok triumphs but moreover fitting these hones to fit nearby settings. This incorporates more prominent center on:

Arrangement Improvement: Building up clear approaches that empower maintainable advancement and ensure critical verifiable locales.

Foundation Enhancements: Overhauling tourism foundation to back maintainable development, decrease natural affect, and progress guest involvement.

Education and Awareness: Upgrading the understanding of supportability issues among both visitors and nearby partners to cultivate a culture of dependable tourism.

Moreover, the integration of lesser-known social locales like St. John Church and the Gumbaz Synagogue into Samarkand primary tourism offerings might differentiate the tourism involvement and disseminate financial benefits more broadly over the community.

As Samarkand moves forward, the part of persistent evaluation and adjustment of methodologies gets to be vital. Locks in with nearby communities, adjusting with worldwide supportability objectives, and cultivating an comprehensive approach to tourism improvement will be basic in guaranteeing that Samarkand not as it were jam its magnificent legacy but too flourishes as a economical tourism goal.

Future Research Directions:

To construct on the discoveries of this ponder, future investigate ought to center on quantitative evaluations of the financial impacts of economical tourism hones, comparative examinations with extra cities that have experienced comparative moves, and the improvement of a show for economical tourism that can be adjusted for utilize in other districts.

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